

Studies in the Synthesis of Alpha Amino Nitriles

J. S. Sandhu, P. S. Sethi and Suresh Mohan

The chemistry of azomethine group has been extensively studied in comparison to carbonyl compounds¹. The nucleophilic addition, addition-elimination and cyclo-addition reactions have received attention during the past few years²⁻⁴. The addition of hydrocyanic acid onto C = N bond of benzylidene aniline and benzylidene-imine was described as early as 1880 by Plochl in unspecified yields⁵. In this paper a convenient synthesis of α -amino nitriles is described and generalised. The yields of the nitriles through both the procedures a and b alongwith their characteristics are recorded in the Table I.

In the earlier method¹ imines were allowed to react with hydrocyanic acid produced *in situ* by the addition of equimolar amounts of potassium cyanide and conc. hydrochloric acid. In the present study it was found that use of hydrochloric acid produced large amount of green resinous material and this could be avoided if glacial acetic acid is used in place of hydrochloric acid.

EXPERIMENTAL

The imines described in this study were prepared as usual and m.pts. agreed with those already recorded in literature. General procedure for HCN addition are

1. R. Layer, *Chem. Rev.* 473, 1963.
2. N. Singh, J. S. Sandhu and Suresh Mohan, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1968, 42, 4453.
3. J. S. Sandhu and Suresh Mohan (unpublished work).
4. N. Singh, Suresh Mohan and J. S. Sandhu, *Chem. Comm.*, 1969, 387.
5. Plochl, *Ber.*, 1880, 1281.

TABLE I

Sr. No.	X	Y	Imine m.p./b.p. °C	Nitrile		Analysis	
				Yield a	% b	m.p. °C	calc. N% found N%
*1.	H	H	52	70	90	91	13.46 13.36
2.	H	p-CH ₃	154 (2.0 mm)	75	85	110	12.61 12.69
3.	H	p-OCH ₃	70	60	80	82	11.76 11.66
4.	H	p-OC ₂ H ₅	76	70	90	71	11.11 11.21
5.	H	p-Cl	62-63	60	95	81	11.55 11.45
6.	p-OCH ₃	H	60-62	70	90	105	11.76 11.68
7.	p-OCH ₃	p-CH ₃	92	75	80	103-104	11.11 11.01
8.	p-OCH ₃	p-OC ₂ H ₅	—	70	90	100	9.93 9.84
9.	p-OCH ₃	p-Cl	—	70	95	101-102	10.27 10.19
10.	p-CH ₃	H	318(760 mm)	60	80	91-92	12.61 12.70

* This nitrile was prepared in unspecified yield

given below :

Procedure A : Benzylidene aniline (0.1 mole) dissolved in ethanol (100 ml) and glacial acetic acid (6.01 ml) was taken in 500 ml round bottom flask. To this sodium cyanide (0.1 mole) solution in water was added dropwise with continuous stirring. The reaction was exothermic and cooling in ice-cold water was necessary. After half a hour the solid obtained was filtered and recrystallised from dilute alcohol, m.p. 91° in 70% yield.

Procedure B : Benzaldehyde (0.1 mole), sodium cyanide solution (0.1 mole) was taken in a beaker containing 50 ml ethanol. Glacial acetic acid (0.1 mole) was added dropwise and aniline (0.1 mole) was added immediately. The reaction mixture was allowed to stand 3-4 hours. The solid separated was filtered and recrystallised from dilute alcohol, m.p. 91° in 90% yield.

Authors wish to record their sincere thanks to the authority of this University for providing facilities.

Chemistry Department,
Panjabi University,
Patiala.

Received 25 April 1970